

Control of a Painting Robot Containing Parallelogram Linkages Based on its Distinctive Dynamic Characteristics

Runtong Sun ^{a,b}, Jun Wu ^{a,b*}, Yanling Tian ^c

^a State Key Laboratory of Tribology in Advanced Equipment and Institute of Manufacturing Engineering, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Tsinghua University, Beijing 100084, China.

^b Beijing Key Lab of Precision/Ultra-precision Manufacturing Equipment and Control, Beijing 100084, China.

^c School of Engineering, University of Warwick, Coventry CV4 7AL, UK.

Abstract

To achieve high-performance control, the dynamics and control should be closely integrated. This paper focuses on dynamic-based control design for a hybrid painting robot containing parallelogram linkages to improve its tracking accuracy and motion consistency. The study derives the dynamics of the parallelogram component to investigate its distinctive attributes, which include time invariance, joint independence, and linear approximability. Based on these unique characteristics, a novel theory-experiment mixed two-step method for control design is presented. It involves identifying and visualizing an optimized space of control parameters through theoretical deduction, followed by determining the optimal control parameters within this space through experimental trials. Experimental results underscore a substantial improvement in the tracking accuracy and motion consistency of the painting robot.

Keywords

Control design; Robot dynamics; Parallelogram linkages; Automatic painting

1 Introduction

Painting robots have been widely used in various industries, such as automobile manufacturing [1-3], airplane production [4,5], furniture fabrication [6], and concrete construction [7]. Their high efficiency and ability to protect workers from hazardous chemicals underscore the advantage over manual labor work [8]. For painting robots, tracking accuracy and motion consistency are critical [9] and directly influence the uniformity of paint thickness [10]. Particularly, proper paint thickness and uniformity are paramount in airplane wing painting for preserving flight performance and safety. Therefore, achieving high-quality painting is a crucial task for painting robots.

In painting applications, serial robots historically dominated the market [11-14]. In recent years, advancements in parallel robot research have unearthed and harnessed their potentials [15,16], such as high stiffness [17-19], high compactness [20], and high motion dynamics [21], facilitating the accomplishment of high-quality painting tasks. For example, a 6-DOF hybrid robot with a 3-DOF parallel mechanism [22], a redundant parallel robot [23], and a cable-driven parallel robot [24] have been proposed for painting tasks. However, the inherent strongly coupled dynamics of most parallel robots present great challenges in control [25], which impedes their widespread applications due to precision concerns. To mitigate coupling effects, parallelogram linkages are incorporated in the design of parallel robots [26-28]. Parallelogram linkages offer independent motion conduction path and introduce some degree of decoupling characteristics to the robot's dynamics [29]. Nevertheless, the planar nature of parallelogram linkages limits their workspace [30,31]. It prompts the addition of a serial part connecting the base and the parallel segment, which effectively combines the advantages of both serial and parallel configurations [32].

In the realm of robotic control, many novel control schemes tailored to specific control objectives have been put forward in recent years. Khadivar [33] proposed a self-correcting quadratic programming-based controller to control a 7-DOF robotic arm, demonstrating effectiveness in unknown model environments. Moreno-Valenzuela [34] put forward a limited integrator anti-windup-based control strategy of input-constrained manipulators. Zhang [35] presented a two-step approach method involving fuzzy relation identification and PID parameter adjustment to optimize the controller. Papadopoulos [36] introduced an optimal tuning method comprising analytical and experimental steps. For painting robots, PID control is the prevailing approach in industrial applications to improve position accuracy and motion consistency [37,38] due to its mature and easy-to-implement characteristics [39]. However, its performance highly depends on control parameters. Typically, two categories of approaches are used to design control parameters: theory-based and experiment-based. The former involves deriving control parameters through theoretical analysis [40,41], with a focus on understanding the robot's dynamics and incorporating them into control. While theoretically sound, this approach faces challenges in

obtaining an accurate mechatronic model, which leads to potentially impractical parameters in real-world scenarios [42,43]. The latter involves fine-tuning control parameters through iterative trials by experienced engineers [44]. While this method can achieve moderate control performance, it lacks a solid theoretical foundation such that the control parameters are suboptimal. Additionally, the tuning process is often tedious and time-consuming. Therefore, there is a need for a novel control design strategy that combines the advantages of both methods mentioned above.

To address the existing problems, this paper investigates the distinctive dynamics of a painting robot containing parallelogram linkages and unveils several intrinsic properties. Leveraging these dynamic characteristics, a theory-experiment hybrid control design approach is proposed to fully harness the strengths of both theoretical analysis and practical trials. Experimental results demonstrate notable enhancements in the tracking accuracy and motion consistency of the painting robot, which affirms the efficacy of the proposed approach.

The remaining parts of the article are organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the robot, which includes its structure, kinematics and dynamics. Section 3 delves into its unique dynamic characteristics, followed by a novel approach to design control parameters in Section 4. Finally, experiments are carried out using the proposed strategy in Section 5, and Section 6 concludes the article.

2 Kinematic and Dynamic Modeling

2.1 Structure Description

Figure 1(a) shows the CAD model of a painting robot containing parallelogram linkages, while Fig. 1(b) provides its schematic diagram. The painting robot comprises two primary parts, a serial rotary table and a planar parallel mechanism. The serial rotary table incorporates two active revolute joints and offers two degrees of freedom (DOFs). The parallel mechanism that consists of a three-parallelogram mechanism provides three DOFs. Notably, the motors driving the parallel component are all mounted around O_2 to reduce dynamic loads induced by themselves.

As shown in Fig. 1(b), a coordinate system $O_2-X_2Y_2Z_2$ is attached to the base of the parallel part. The motors in this part drive the spray gun to move along the X_2 and Y_2 axes and rotate around the Z_2 axis through the three-parallelogram mechanism, namely, $O_2ABO_3(O_4)$, O_2CDO_3 , and $O_3EFO_4(O_5)$. Specifically, two motors drive O_2O_3 and O_2A of the first parallelogram $O_2ABO_3(O_4)$, respectively, while another motor drives O_2C of the second parallelogram O_2CDO_3 , whose motion is then transmitted to the third parallelogram $O_3EFO_4(O_5)$ via a triangle structure DO_3E . The three-parallelogram mechanism ensures independent transmission paths for each motor. Thus, the robot has the decoupling driving characteristics. To extend the workspace of the robot, the parallelogram part is built upon a 2-DOF serial base. The serial part can rotate around two axes, Z_0 and Z_1 , which are perpendicular to each other.

Fig. 1. Painting robot. (a) CAD view. (b) Schematic diagram.

2.2 Kinematic Model

Due to the presence of parallelogram linkages, the hybrid painting robot can be treated as a serial mechanism when analyzing its kinematics. Coordinate frames are assigned according to the Denavit-Hartenberg (DH) convention [45], as shown in Fig. 2. The joints, links, and coordinate systems with low transparency represent the robot's serial equivalence, while those with high transparency make up the parallel part of the robot. The z axes of each local coordinate system in the parallel section are all parallel to the Z_2 axis, and the y axes follow the right-hand rule, so they are both omitted for clarity.

Fig. 2. The coordinate frames of the painting robot.

The DH parameters of the robot are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

DH parameters of the robot.

Joint	α_i (°)	a_i (mm)	d_i (mm)	θ_i (°)
O_1	-90	0	0	θ_z
O_2	90	0	h	θ_y
O_3	0	l_1	0	θ_1
O_4	0	l_2	0	$-\theta_1 + \theta_2 - 180$
O_5	0	l_3	0	$-\theta_2 + \theta_3 - \beta$
A	0	l_4	0	θ_2
B	0	l_1	0	$\theta_1 - \theta_2$
C	0	l_5	0	θ_3
D	0	l_1	0	$\theta_1 - \theta_3$
E	0	l_6	0	$-\theta_1 + \theta_3 + \zeta - 180$
F	0	l_2	0	$\theta_2 - \theta_3 - \zeta$

Therefore, the position $\mathbf{p} = [p_x \ p_y \ p_z]^T$ and direction $\mathbf{d} = [d_x \ d_y \ d_z]^T$ of the spray gun with respect to $O_0-X_0Y_0Z_0$ can be derived as

$$\begin{cases}
p_x = s\theta_z [-l_1s\theta_1 + l_2s\theta_2 + l_3s(\theta_3 - \beta) - h] + c\theta_z c\theta_y [l_1c\theta_1 - l_2c\theta_2 - l_3c(\theta_3 - \beta)] \\
p_y = c\theta_z [l_1s\theta_1 - l_2s\theta_2 - l_3s(\theta_3 - \beta) + h] + s\theta_z c\theta_y [l_1c\theta_1 - l_2c\theta_2 - l_3c(\theta_3 - \beta)] \\
p_z = s\theta_y [-l_1c\theta_1 + l_2c\theta_2 + l_3c(\theta_3 - \beta)] \\
d_x = s(\theta_3 - \beta)s\theta_z - c(\theta_3 - \beta)c\theta_z c\theta_y \\
d_y = -s(\theta_3 - \beta)c\theta_z - c(\theta_3 - \beta)s\theta_z c\theta_y \\
d_z = c(\theta_3 - \beta)s\theta_y
\end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where s , c and t represent sine, cosine and tangent functions, respectively. Unlike general hybrid robots, no coupling term among θ_1 , θ_2 and θ_3 is observed in Eq. (1), which showcases the decoupling kinematics brought by parallelogram linkages. Based on Eq. (1), θ_z , θ_3 and θ_y can be sequentially solved as follows when $d_z^2 + p_z^2 \neq 0$.

$$\begin{cases}
\theta_z = \arctan \left[\frac{(d_x p_z - d_z p_x)}{(d_y p_z - d_z p_y)} \right] \\
\theta_3 = \beta + \arcsin(d_x s\theta_z - d_y c\theta_z) \\
\theta_y = \begin{cases} \text{sign} \left[\frac{d_z}{c(\theta_3 - \beta)} \right] \arccos \left[-\frac{(d_x c\theta_z + d_y s\theta_z)}{c(\theta_3 - \beta)} \right] & c(\theta_3 - \beta) \neq 0 \\ -\arctan \left[\frac{p_z / p_x c\theta_z + p_y s\theta_z}{p_z} \right] & c(\theta_3 - \beta) = 0 \end{cases}
\end{cases} \quad (2)$$

If $d_z^2 + p_z^2 = 0$, it can be solved that

$$\begin{cases}
\theta_z = 0 \\
\theta_y = 0 \\
\theta_3 = \beta + \text{atan2}(d_z, d_1) - (\text{sign } d_z) \pi
\end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where atan2 is a MATLAB function solving for four quadrant inverse tangent. After solving for the driving angles in the serial part, the homogeneous transform matrix T from $O_0-X_0Y_0Z_0$ to $O_2-X_2Y_2Z_2$ is determined as

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{O}_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta_z c\theta_y & -s\theta_z & c\theta_z s\theta_y & -hs\theta_z \\ s\theta_z c\theta_y & c\theta_z & s\theta_z s\theta_y & hc\theta_z \\ -s\theta_y & 0 & c\theta_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{R} is the rotation matrix and \mathbf{O}_2 is the position vector of O_2 in $O_0-X_0Y_0Z_0$. Consequently, the position vector of the spray gun with respect to $O_2-X_2Y_2Z_2$ is

$$\mathbf{p}' = T^{-1} \mathbf{p} \quad (5)$$

By applying the DH method to the equivalent serial model of the parallel part, \mathbf{p}' can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases}
pp_x = l_1c\theta_1 - l_2c\theta_2 - l_3c(\theta_3 - \beta) \\
pp_y = l_1s\theta_1 - l_2s\theta_2 - l_3s(\theta_3 - \beta) \\
pp_z = 0
\end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where pp_x, pp_y and pp_z represent the component of \mathbf{p}' along X_2, Y_2 and Z_2 axes, respectively. Let $\gamma = \theta_2 - \theta_1$ and substitute into Eq. (6), γ can be solved as

$$\gamma = \arccos \frac{[pp_x + l_3c(\theta_3 - \beta)]^2 + [pp_y + l_3s(\theta_3 - \beta)]^2 - l_1^2 - l_2^2}{-2l_1l_2} \quad (7)$$

Replacing θ_2 with $(\theta_1 + \gamma)$ in pp_x of Eq. (6) and considering the mechanical constraints, θ_1 and θ_2 can be determined by

$$\begin{cases} \theta_1 = -\arcsin\left\{\frac{[pp_x + l_3 c(\theta_3 - \beta)]}{[l_2^2 s^2 \gamma + (l_1 - l_2 c \gamma)^2]^{1/2}}\right\} - \text{atan2}(l_1 - l_2 c \gamma, l_2 s \gamma) + \pi \\ \theta_2 = \theta_1 + \gamma \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

2.3 Dynamic Model of the Parallelogram Part

A link coordinate system $L_i-x_i y_i z_i$ is attached to one end of each link with x_i aligning with the link's longitudinal direction and z_i perpendicular to the $X_2-O_2-Y_2$ plane. Therefore, the center of mass of each link O_{Ci} with respect to $O_2-X_2 Y_2 Z_2$ can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{O}_{Ci} = \left[\sum_{j=1}^3 \Psi_{ij} c \psi_{ij} \quad \sum_{j=1}^3 \Psi_{ij} s \psi_{ij} \quad \Upsilon_i \right]^T \quad (9)$$

where $\psi_{ij} = \theta_j + \phi_{ij}$. The subscript j takes values of 1, 2, or 3 depending on the value of i . Ψ_{ij} , ϕ_{ij} and Υ_i are constants related to each link, which can be determined by measuring the CAD model. Therefore, the relation between joint velocity and end velocity is

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{v}_{Ci} = \mathbf{J}_{vi} \dot{\mathbf{q}} \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}_i = \mathbf{J}_{oi} \dot{\mathbf{q}} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{q} = [\theta_z \quad \theta_y \quad \theta_1 \quad \theta_2 \quad \theta_3]^T$, and $\mathbf{J}_{oi} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -s\theta_z & \delta_i c\theta_z s\theta_y & \varepsilon_i c\theta_z s\theta_y & \eta_i c\theta_z s\theta_y \\ 0 & c\theta_z & \delta_i s\theta_z s\theta_y & \varepsilon_i s\theta_z s\theta_y & \eta_i s\theta_z s\theta_y \\ 1 & 0 & \delta_i c\theta_y & \varepsilon_i c\theta_y & \eta_i c\theta_y \end{bmatrix}$,

$$\mathbf{J}_{vi} = \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial \theta_z} \mathbf{O}_{Ci} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{O}_2}{\partial \theta_z} \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial \theta_y} \mathbf{O}_{Ci} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{O}_2}{\partial \theta_y} \quad \mathbf{R} \mathbf{J}_{vi}^p \right], \text{ and } \mathbf{J}_{vi}^p = \begin{bmatrix} -\Psi_{i1} s \psi_{i1} & -\Psi_{i2} s \psi_{i2} & -\Psi_{i3} s \psi_{i3} \\ \Psi_{i1} c \psi_{i1} & \Psi_{i2} c \psi_{i2} & \Psi_{i3} c \psi_{i3} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \text{ One value of } \delta_i, \varepsilon_i \text{ and } \eta_i \text{ is 1}$$

and the others are 0 based on the value of i . \mathbf{J}_{vi}^p does not have a coupling term among different actuating angles, which is the key to enable the decoupling dynamics of the parallelogram part. Based on Eq. (10), the dynamic model of the robot can be established as

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{V} + \mathbf{G} \quad (11)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau}$, \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{V} , and \mathbf{G} are the actuating torque, inertia term, centrifugal and Coriolis term, and gravitational term, respectively. Their values and be solved as

$$\mathbf{M} = \sum_i \left(m_i \mathbf{J}_{vi}^T \mathbf{J}_{vi} + \mathbf{J}_{oi}^T \mathbf{I}_{Ci} \mathbf{J}_{oi} \right), \quad \mathbf{V} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{j=1}^5 \sum_{k=1}^5 \left(\frac{\partial M_{1j}}{\partial q_k} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial M_{jk}}{\partial q_1} \right) \dot{q}_k \dot{q}_j \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{j=1}^5 \sum_{k=1}^5 \left(\frac{\partial M_{nj}}{\partial q_k} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial M_{jk}}{\partial q_n} \right) \dot{q}_k \dot{q}_j \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{G} = -\sum_i m_i \mathbf{J}_{vi}^T \mathbf{g} \quad (12)$$

where m_i and \mathbf{I}_{Ci} represent the mass and inertia matrix of Link i , respectively, and $\mathbf{g} = [0 \quad g \quad 0]^T$ is the gravitational acceleration.

3 Decoupling and Time-Invariant Characteristics of the Robot Dynamics

Robot dynamics serve as the foundation for high-precision control. However, for the vast majority of hybrid robots, each element of \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{G} matrix is typically time-variant, which means that control systems with fixed parameters face challenges to fit the robot's dynamics. In order to conduct control design for a hybrid robot containing parallelogram linkages, a more in-depth investigation into its dynamics is warranted.

3.1 Inertia Term

In Eq. (12), the parallel part of \mathbf{M} , i.e., the submatrix of the last three columns and rows, is

$$\mathbf{M}^P = \sum_i \left(m_i \begin{bmatrix} \Psi_{i1}^2 & \Psi_{i12} c\psi_{i12} & \Psi_{i13} c\psi_{i13} \\ \Psi_{i12} c\psi_{i12} & \Psi_{i2}^2 & \Psi_{i23} c\psi_{i23} \\ \Psi_{i13} c\psi_{i13} & \Psi_{i23} c\psi_{i23} & \Psi_{i3}^2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \delta_i I_{zzi} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon_i I_{zzi} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \eta_i I_{zzi} \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (13)$$

where I_{zzi} is the moment of inertia around the Z_2 axis of Link i with respect to its center of mass. For simplicity, Ψ_{ips} represents $\Psi_{ip}\Psi_{is}$ and ψ_{ips} represents the difference between ψ_{ip} and ψ_{is} . Based on Eq. (13), several properties of the inertia term can be derived as follows:

- 1) Each element of \mathbf{M}^P is independent of the serial part's structure.
- 2) The diagonal terms are time-invariant and related to the design of the parallel part only.
- 3) The off-diagonal terms in \mathbf{M}^P are solely connected to the difference between actuating angles of two joints in the parallel part.

These properties are visually demonstrated in Fig. 3. In Fig. 3, the off-diagonal terms in the upper triangular part of \mathbf{M}^P are specifically depicted given its symmetry and constant diagonal terms. M_{12}^P is plotted against θ_1 and θ_2 due to its independence from θ_3 . Similarly, M_{13}^P is plotted against θ_1 and θ_3 , while M_{23}^P is plotted against θ_2 and θ_3 . As shown in Fig. 3, the contours for M_{jk}^P ($j \neq k$), depicted in red dotted line, are linear with respect to the difference between θ_j and θ_k .

Fig. 3. Elements in \mathbf{M}^P versus θ_1 , θ_2 , and θ_3 .

Another important property of \mathbf{M}^P lies in its decoupling characteristics. To quantitatively assess this feature, an inertia coupling index (ICI) is defined as

$$ICI_i = \frac{|M_{ii}^P|}{\sum_{i=j}^3 |M_{ij}^P|} \quad (14)$$

The range of ICI_i spans from 0 to 1, with higher values suggesting reduced coupling effects. Notably, when ICI_i equals 0.5, the inertia force comes from Joint i itself is the same as that of other joints assuming identical accelerations of the joints. Consequently, when ICI_i surpasses 0.5, the inertia force attributed to the joint itself exceeds that of all other joints combined. As a result, 0.5 is selected as the threshold for assessing inertia coupling effects. If all elements of ICI are larger than 0.5, \mathbf{M}^P is considered diagonally dominant in mathematics, which means that the inertia force of an active joint is predominantly influenced by itself. Consequently, this joint is decoupled from others in terms of inertia force. ICI versus θ_1 , θ_2 , and θ_3 is calculated and plotted in Fig. 4. As shown in Fig. 4, ICI_1 , ICI_2 and ICI_3 all exceed 0.5 in most areas of the robot's workspace. Therefore, it's reasonable to disregard other joints when studying the inertia force of one joint.

Fig. 4. ICI of M^P versus θ_1 , θ_2 , and θ_3 .

3.2 Gravitational Term

Based on Eq. (12), the last three elements of \mathbf{G} that constitute its parallel part can be written as

$$\mathbf{G}^P = -\sum_i m_i g \begin{bmatrix} \Psi_{i1} c\psi_{i1} c\theta_z - \Psi_{i1} s\psi_{i1} c\theta_y s\theta_z \\ \Psi_{i2} c\psi_{i2} c\theta_z - \Psi_{i2} s\psi_{i2} c\theta_y s\theta_z \\ \Psi_{i3} c\psi_{i3} c\theta_z - \Psi_{i3} s\psi_{i3} c\theta_y s\theta_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

From Eq. (15), it can be concluded that: 1) The gravitational force of joints in the parallel part does not affect each other. 2) The serial part affects all joints in the parallel part in the same manner.

Elements in \mathbf{G}^P around the painting working space is visualized in Fig. 5. From Fig. 5, one may see that \mathbf{G}_i^P can be approximated to lie on a plane perpendicular to the $\theta_i - \mathbf{G}_i^P$ plane.

Fig. 5. Elements in \mathbf{G}^P versus θ_z , θ_y , and θ_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$).

Take Joint 3 as an example, \mathbf{G}_3^P around $\theta_1 = \theta_{10}$ can be approximated by

$$\mathbf{G}_3^P \approx \left\{ -\sum_i m_i g \Psi_{i1} \begin{bmatrix} c\theta_z c(\theta_{10} + \varphi_{i1}) - c\theta_y s\theta_z s(\theta_{10} + \varphi_{i1}) \\ + c\theta_z s(\theta_{10} + \varphi_{i1})\theta_{10} + c\theta_y s\theta_z c(\theta_{10} + \varphi_{i1})\theta_{10} \end{bmatrix} \right\} + \left\{ \sum_i m_i g \Psi_{i1} \begin{bmatrix} c\theta_z s(\theta_{10} + \varphi_{i1}) + c\theta_y s\theta_z c(\theta_{10} + \varphi_{i1}) \end{bmatrix} \right\} \theta_1 \quad (16)$$

Because both θ_z and θ_y do not change dramatically along the painting trajectory, they can be treated as constants with acceptable deviations in approximating \mathbf{G}_3^P . Therefore, the first term of \mathbf{G}_3^P , which is in the first curly brace in Eq. (16), is a constant, while the second term is proportional to θ_1 . In this way, \mathbf{G}_3^P can be approximated by a linear function of θ_1 using the Least Squares Method. Similarly, \mathbf{G}_2^P and \mathbf{G}_1^P can be approximated by linear functions. The approximation of

G_i^p can be written as $\hat{G}_i^p = k_i \theta_i + b_i$. The values of k_i and b_i , and the errors between G_i^p and \hat{G}_i^p are shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Parameters in the approximation of \hat{G}_i^p .

i	k_i	b_i	average error	mean absolute percentage error
1	-0.3329	30.6466	3.4832	30.8339%
2	0.0056	0.9012	0.0034	2.5985%
3	-0.0088	0.9266	0.0028	6.3930%

\hat{G}_i^p is shown in Fig. 5 with black edges. The mean percentage errors of \hat{G}_2^p and \hat{G}_3^p are less than 10%, while that of \hat{G}_1^p is slightly larger. However, it's already a close enough approximation for further control design. Therefore, this linear approximation can replace Eq. (15) in calculating G^p .

3.3 Centrifugal and Coriolis Term

From Eq. (12), the parallel parts of V can be calculated as

$$V^p = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\theta}_2^2 \sum_i \Psi_{i12} s \Psi_{i12} + \dot{\theta}_3^2 \sum_i \Psi_{i13} s \Psi_{i13} \\ -\dot{\theta}_1^2 \sum_i \Psi_{i12} s \Psi_{i12} + \dot{\theta}_3^2 \sum_i \Psi_{i23} s \Psi_{i23} \\ -\dot{\theta}_1^2 \sum_i \Psi_{i13} s \Psi_{i13} - \dot{\theta}_2^2 \sum_i \Psi_{i23} s \Psi_{i23} \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

There's no term as $\dot{\theta}_j \dot{\theta}_k$ ($j \neq k$) in Eq. (17), which means that the speed of joints in the parallel part only affects the actuating torque independently. Therefore, decoupling characteristics can also be observed in the centrifugal and Coriolis term. However, in most applications including painting scenarios, centrifugal and Coriolis force accounts for a negligible amount of the total actuating force [29]. Therefore, this term is omitted in later analysis.

The decoupling and time-invariant characteristics deduced above result from the absence of a coupling term among active joints in the parallel part of the robot's kinematics. Importantly, these characteristics remain consistent regardless of the structure of the serial part. Hence, the proposed method demonstrates universal applicability for any hybrid robot sharing the same parallelogram part connecting the end effector and the base through various serial mechanisms.

4 Novel Two-Step Approach for Control Design

In industrial applications, PID control stands out as one of the most commonly used control methods, which demonstrates high efficacy under well-tuned control parameters. However, the process of obtaining suitable control parameters traditionally relies heavily on experiential knowledge. It lacks a robust theoretical foundation to consider the changes of the robot's dynamics. The reliance on empirical tuning not only renders the tuning task laborious but also introduces potential hazards when incorrect parameters are selected. Moreover, the dynamics of conventional robots are intricately affected by the robot's pose, making a set of parameters suitable for one pose but not necessarily applicable to others. To address these challenges and leverage the inherent advantages of decoupling and time-invariant dynamics within parallelogram linkages, a novel two-step approach for designing control parameters is proposed. In the first step, an optimized space of control parameters is identified and visualized through theoretical deductions. In the second step, the optimal control parameters are refined within this space through experimental practice.

4.1 PID Control Scheme Considering Robotic Dynamics

In the painting robot, a closed-loop PID controller is used, as shown in Fig. 6. The current loop is typically fine-tuned and can be treated as a unit gain in our research. The position loop adopts proportional (P) control with a proportional gain of K_p , while the velocity loop uses proportional-integral (PI) control with a speed loop gain of K_v and an integral time constant of T_i . T_d is the disturbance injected into the control loop, which is the dynamic loads on the motor shaft. As discussed in Section 3, T_d of Joint 3 can be written as

$$T_d = \sum_{j=1}^3 M_{1j}^p \ddot{\theta}_j + V_1^p + G_1^p \quad (18)$$

Fig. 6. Block diagram of the PID control scheme.

Hereafter, Joint 3 is taken as an example to illustrate the control design method, given the similarity in dynamics and control among the three joints in the parallelogram linkages. It's worth noting that friction force also affects T_d , but it can be compensated by the friction compensation module in the motor drive. Hence, friction is not explicitly considered in our discussion.

Based on Eq. (18), the transfer function of the equivalent control system can be deduced as

$$\theta_{out} = \underbrace{\frac{K_p K_v K_T s + K_p K_v K_T / T_v}{D(s)}}_{\text{uncoupling term}} \theta_{in} - \underbrace{\frac{(M_{12}^p \theta_2 s^3 + M_{13}^p \theta_3 s^3 + V_1^p s) / N^2}{D(s)}}_{\text{coupling term}} - \underbrace{\frac{b_1 s / N^2}{D(s)}}_{\text{constant term}} \quad (19)$$

where $D(s) = (J + M_{11}^p / N^2) s^3 + (K_v K_T + B) s^2 + (K_v K_T / T_v + K_p K_v K_T + k_1 / N^2) s + K_p K_v K_T / T_v$ and N is the reduction ratio of the motor.

Equation (19) can be divided into the following three terms. 1) An uncoupling term. It's only relevant to the current joint. 2) A coupling term. It's affected by other joints, but can be neglected due to its relatively small value compared to the uncoupling term. 3) A constant term. It arises from the linear approximation of gravity, which can be compensated using the gravity compensation module in the motor driver. Therefore, only the uncoupling term should be taken into account in control design, which renders the transfer function decoupling and time-invariant.

4.2 Performance Index

Utilizing the decoupling and time-invariant mechatronic model, the control parameters can be designed with universal effectiveness across the entire workspace. In order to achieve better performance of the robot, several indices in control design are put forward.

4.2.1 Stability Index

Stability is the fundamental requirement for a control system, which can be judged through the eigenvalues of the characteristic equation $D(s) = 0$. For conventional robots, stability at one pose does not inherently guarantee stability at other poses due to the time-varying nature of $D(s)$. However, the characteristic equation is time-independent for the painting robot, which means the system is stable throughout the entire workspace once it is stable at a specific pose. Using Routh's stability criterion, the control system is stable if the following inequalities are satisfied.

$$\begin{cases} J + \frac{M_{11}^p}{N^2} > 0, \frac{K_v K_T}{T_v} + K_p K_v K_T + \frac{k_1}{N^2} > 0, K_v K_T + B > 0, \frac{K_p K_v K_T}{T_v} > 0 \\ \left[\frac{k_1}{N^2} + K_v K_T \left(K_p + \frac{1}{T_v} \right) \right] (K_v K_T + B) - \frac{K_p K_v K_T (J + M_{11}^p / N^2)}{T_v} > 0 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where k_1 is negative while other parameters are all positive. Consequently, except for the second and last inequalities in Eq. (20), other inequalities naturally hold true. Therefore, the stability index (SI) for control design is

$$SI = \frac{1}{\lambda} \min \left(\left[\frac{k_1}{N^2} + K_v K_T \left(K_p + \frac{1}{T_v} \right) \right] - \frac{K_p K_v K_T (J + M_{11}^p / N^2)}{T_v (K_v K_T + B)}, \frac{K_v K_T}{T_v} + K_p K_v K_T + \frac{k_1}{N^2} \right) \quad (21)$$

where λ is a scaling factor. Normally, SI should be greater than zero to satisfy the stability condition. However, in practice, the threshold is set higher to compensate for inevitable discrepancies between the theoretical model and the real system.

4.2.2 Error Mapping Index

The control error is defined as the difference between θ_{in} and θ_{out} , which can be calculated using the formula

$$\theta_e = \frac{-(J + M_{11}^p/N^2)s^3 - (K_v K_T + B)s^2 - (K_v K_T/T_v + k_1/N^2)s}{(J + M_{11}^p/N^2)s^3 + (K_v K_T + B)s^2 + (K_v K_T/T_v + K_p K_v K_T + k_1/N^2)s + K_p K_v K_T/T_v} \theta_{in} \quad (22)$$

For the painting robot, the input signal operates at a low frequency, resulting in $|s| \ll 1$. Therefore, the higher-order terms in the denominator of Eq. (22) can be neglected. Taking the inverse Laplace transform, the error expression becomes

$$\theta_e = -\frac{(J + M_{11}^p/N^2)T_v}{K_p K_v K_T} \ddot{\theta}_{in} - \frac{(K_v K_T + B)T_v}{K_p K_v K_T} \dot{\theta}_{in} - \frac{K_v K_T N^2 + k_1 T_v}{K_p K_v K_T N^2} \dot{\theta}_{in} \quad (23)$$

Equation (23) shows that velocity, acceleration and jerk of the required joint motion all influence the final error. Smoother motion trajectories can be designed to mitigate these influences. Additionally, control parameters can be optimized to minimize the coefficients before these three terms to reduce the control error. An error mapping index (EMI) is defined as

$$EMI = \lambda_1 \frac{(J + M_{11}^p/N^2)T_v}{K_p K_v K_T} + \lambda_2 \frac{(K_v K_T + B)T_v}{K_p K_v K_T} + \lambda_3 \left| \frac{K_v K_T N^2 + k_1 T_v}{K_p K_v K_T N^2} \right| \quad (24)$$

where λ_1 , λ_2 and λ_3 are the coefficients proportional to velocity, acceleration, and jerk values in the painting trajectory, respectively.

4.2.3 Other Indices

In addition to stability and precision, rapidity and bandwidth are also crucial for the comprehensive performance of a control system. Settling time, indicative of both rapidity and stability, is defined as the time it takes for the error to remain below 2% of the difference between the final and initial values in a step response. This parameter is expressed as the settling time index (STI). Bandwidth, on the other hand, represents the frequency range wherein the magnitude of the closed-loop frequency response is greater than -3 dB and is denoted as the bandwidth index (BI).

Beyond our efforts to align the control system with our expectations, there are some constraints on control parameters imposed by the motor manufacturer that must be followed. These restrictions are encapsulated in three motor indices (MI₁, MI₂, and MI₃) as follows

$$MI_1 = 2\pi K_v / K_p, MI_2 = 2\pi K_v T_v, MI_3 = 1000 / (2\pi K_v T_R) \quad (25)$$

where T_R is the first stage first torque reference filter time constant and its default value is kept in our experiment.

4.3 Theory-Experiment Mixed Two-Step Method

The process of designing control parameters is about striking a balance among different performance indices, where improving one index often entails a trade-off with another. For instance, the increase of K_p for a larger BI may concurrently raise STI, which is undesirable. Therefore, it's crucial to provide an intuitive interface in engineering practice for designing control parameter. In order to ensure that the robot functions as expected, experience-based criteria for these indices are imposed. These criteria allow for a certain degree of fluctuation in practice. Consequently, in the first step of the presented method, an optimized three-dimensional space instead of three fixed control parameters is determined by theoretical analysis. Subsequently, in the second step, a set of exact control parameters is obtained from their candidate values in the optimized space through experimental trials. In this way, the theory-experiment mixed approach has the advantages of both theoretical and experimental methods. It maximizes the advantages of the robot's decoupling and time-independent dynamics, which enables us to determine an optimized candidate space of control parameters regardless of the robot's pose and motion. In addition, it capitalizes on the strengths of engineering practice, which can obtain the best set of control parameters through several experiments.

To illustrate the above method, Joint 3 is used as an example. Based on engineering practice, the criteria for the indices are specified as

$$SI > 2, EMI < 5, STI < 1.1, BI > 170, MI_1 > 4, MI_2 > 40, MI_3 > 0.8 \quad (26)$$

Utilizing these criteria, the optimized three-dimensional candidate space for control parameters is found, as shown in Fig. 7. The boundary of the candidate space comprises contour planes of different indices, with their detailed values provided in subfigures around the central one. Control parameters in darker colors are deemed more desirable than those in lighter colors. In the central plot, the red space enclosed by the boundaries of contour planes represents the optimized space, from which control parameters are finalized by taking trial experiments.

Fig. 7. Optimized candidate space for control parameters of Joint 3.

5 Experiments

5.1 Experiment Setups

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed method, experiments are carried out on the prototype of a 5-DOF painting robot with parallelogram linkages. The robot's five motors are manufactured by YASKAWA and driven by SERVOPACKS, which possess three-loop PID control schemes. The trajectory for the verification experiments is designed to simulate the actual painting process of the airplane's wing, which features a near S-shaped curved. Two different painting strategies are adopted in the experiment, with a 90° difference in direction, as shown in Fig. 8. While the robot moves along the painting trajectory, the spray gun only operates along the longer side of the trajectory, which is highlighted in red in Fig. 8. Precision in this part of the trajectory is of paramount importance, which is designated as Trajectory 1' and Trajectory 2' in the ensuing analysis.

Fig. 8. Control design and experimental process diagram.

5.2 Experiment Results

Prior to the verification experiments, two sets of control parameters for three joints in the parallel part were obtained. Control Parameter Set 1 was either meticulously tuned by experienced engineers or configured using the autotuning methods embedded in SERVOPACKs, depending on their control performances. Control Parameter Set 2 was designed using the proposed method, which involves fine-tuning the control parameters through single-axis experiments within the optimized control parameter candidate space obtained by theoretical analysis. The control parameters for these two sets are listed in Table 3, and experiments are carried out on Trajectory 1 and Trajectory 2 using these control parameters. For each trajectory, two different operating speeds are employed.

Table 3

Control parameters.

Control Parameter Set	Joint number	$K_p (\times 10^{-1})$	$K_v (\times 10^{-1})$	$T_v (\times 10^{-5})$
1	3	2000	1500	50000
	4	1800	1600	48000
	5	AUTOTUNING		
2	3	1900	1700	12500
	4	2100	2000	8000
	5	2200	1800	3000

5.2.1 Tracking Error Analysis

The tracking errors of the painting robot on Trajectory 1 and 2 at low operating speed are depicted in Figs. 9 and 10, respectively, while those at high operating speed are shown in Figs. 11 and 12, respectively.

Fig. 9. Tracking errors on Trajectory 1 under low operating speed. (a)-(c) Following error of Joints 3, 4 and 5, with the left y-axis represents the error associated with different control parameters and the right y-axis displays the joint position. (d) End position error of the robot. (e) End position error considering the parallel part only. (f) End direction error of the robot. (g) End direction error considering the parallel part only.

Fig. 10. Tracking errors on Trajectory 2 under low operating speed. (a)-(c) Following error of Joints 3, 4 and 5, with the left y-axis represents the error associated with different control parameters and the right y-axis displays the joint position. (d) End position error of the robot. (e) End position error considering the parallel part only. (f) End direction error of the robot. (g) End direction error considering the parallel part only.

Fig. 11. Tracking errors on Trajectory 1 under high operating speed. (a)-(c) Following error of Joints 3, 4 and 5, with the left y-axis represents the error associated with different control parameters and the right y-axis displays the joint position. (d) End position error of the robot. (e) End position error considering the parallel part only. (f) End direction error of the robot. (g) End direction error considering the parallel part only.

Fig. 12. Tracking errors on Trajectory 2 under high operating speed. (a)-(c) Following error of Joints 3, 4 and 5, with the left y-axis represents the error associated with different control parameters and the right y-axis displays the joint position. (d) End position error of the robot. (e) End position error considering the parallel part only. (f) End direction error of the robot. (g) End direction error considering the parallel part only.

Figures 9 to 12 demonstrate a significant reduction in tracking errors achieved by using the proposed method to design control parameters, both at high and low operating speeds. Due to wearing and backlash problems of Joint 2, its precision is significantly lower than other joints. In order to accurately reflect the true efficacy of the proposed method, the end error that only considers the parallel part is also presented in (e) and (g). Detailed experimental data is shown in Tables 4 and 5, where Δq_i denotes the tracking error of Joint i , Δs_{end} and $\Delta \theta_{\text{end}}$ represent the position and direction error of the spray gun, and the notation ' after Δ signifies that the error is measured without consideration of the serial part.

Under low operating speeds, the average errors in the position and direction of the spray gun for Trajectory 1 decrease by 5.1% and 15.6%, respectively, while Trajectory 2 shows reductions of 2.1% and 23.8%. When excluding the serial part, whose control parameter optimization is not considered in this paper, errors of the spray gun exhibit further reductions, with a decline of 25.5% in position error and 18.3% in direction error for Trajectory 1. Trajectory 2 also experiences a 14.7% decrease in position error and a 43.5% drop in direction error. In this case, maximum errors, which reflect the worst-case painting scenarios, decrease by approximately 36.9% and 26.5% in position for two trajectories and 22.8% and 42.3% in direction. Under high operating speed, the position and direction errors for Trajectory 1 witness decline of 35.1% and 59.9%, respectively, while Trajectory 2 experiences reductions of 37.2% and 28.4%.

These errors encompass the entire moving session of the robot. If we specifically consider the painting session, errors witness further reduction due to more stable movement during this phase.

Though decreased significantly, errors still exist due to several contributing factors. First, the inherent nature of PID control schemes, as indicated by Eq. (23), means that errors can only be minimized but not entirely eliminated. This is intrinsic to closed-loop systems. Secondly, the calculation of gravitational force, as approximated in Eq. (16) by omitting higher-order terms in the Taylor expansion, inevitably introduces errors. Thirdly, imperfections in the mechanical structure, such as gear backlash and joint clearance, contribute to errors. Additionally, environmental factors such as vibrations also contribute to the generation of errors.

Table 4
Average tracking errors.

Trajectory	Speed	Control Parameter Set	Δq_3 ($\times 10^{-3}$ °)	Δq_4 ($\times 10^{-3}$ °)	Δq_5 ($\times 10^{-3}$ °)	Δs_{end} ($\times 10^{-5}$ m)	$\Delta \theta_{end}$ ($\times 10^{-3}$ °)	$\Delta s'_{end}$ ($\times 10^{-5}$ m)	$\Delta \theta'_{end}$ ($\times 10^{-3}$ °)
1	Low	1	4.3022	5.3242	3.1066	10.2921	3.4165	5.0204	3.1066
		2	3.9966	2.8668	2.5384	9.7675	2.8824	3.7391	2.5384
	High	1	6.7749	7.8208	5.9660	12.4738	6.0938	7.4276	5.9660
		2	4.9628	4.3183	3.8067	8.9025	3.9266	4.8678	3.8067
2	Low	1	2.9859	3.1947	1.4134	8.7577	1.7098	3.3439	1.4134
		2	2.8673	2.0802	0.7986	8.5734	1.3021	2.8508	0.7986
	High	1	3.5803	3.4517	1.4649	11.0664	1.7456	3.8758	1.4649
		2	2.3762	2.0659	1.0490	8.1682	1.3140	2.4325	1.0490
1'	Low	1	2.9808	4.6273	1.6844	4.4729	1.9097	4.0973	1.6844
		2	1.7788	1.6401	0.4853	2.7193	0.9669	1.8888	0.4853
	High	1	2.7395	2.7810	1.6412	5.0237	1.6185	2.8531	1.6007
		2	1.3491	1.9223	0.5072	4.1908	0.8362	1.8518	0.6411
2'	Low	1	1.4295	1.9013	0.7854	2.0850	1.0393	1.7929	0.7854
		2	1.1664	0.8107	0.2341	1.6052	0.7852	1.1812	0.2341
	High	1	0.7911	1.3890	0.2498	4.7971	0.4824	1.2081	0.2498
		2	0.4574	0.5525	0.0741	4.1496	0.5437	0.5780	0.0741

Table 5
Maximum tracking errors.

Trajectory	Speed	Control Parameter Set	Δq_3 ($\times 10^{-3}$ °)	Δq_4 ($\times 10^{-3}$ °)	Δq_5 ($\times 10^{-3}$ °)	Δs_{end} ($\times 10^{-5}$ m)	$\Delta \theta_{end}$ ($\times 10^{-3}$ °)	$\Delta s'_{end}$ ($\times 10^{-5}$ m)	$\Delta \theta'_{end}$ ($\times 10^{-3}$ °)
1	Low	1	18.0556	31.5250	14.0086	32.2011	15.3779	20.7224	14.0086
		2	13.9409	13.1840	10.8157	30.7167	11.1311	13.0690	10.8157
	High	1	20.8667	32.7997	20.6684	33.9993	20.6684	22.6221	20.6684
		2	14.1470	11.9093	9.7784	20.8614	10.5414	12.9608	9.7784
2	Low	1	13.2415	25.8767	7.5651	30.6403	8.1230	17.2478	7.5651
		2	13.1417	13.6971	4.3672	30.4726	5.3654	12.6759	4.3672
	High	1	18.2687	21.4321	6.6640	39.4965	6.6671	17.9922	6.6640
		2	12.3391	9.1316	5.0312	20.8983	5.4689	11.7400	5.0312
1'	Low	1	6.9845	15.3143	5.2571	10.9956	7.0592	10.8593	5.2571
		2	4.8741	7.0458	1.8895	7.4737	2.6320	5.1314	1.8895
	High	1	7.0407	7.1631	4.7838	15.4795	4.8048	6.1001	4.7838
		2	4.7776	4.4729	2.7350	12.2394	3.0691	3.9199	2.7350
2'	Low	1	11.3762	9.1114	3.4359	11.6741	3.4359	11.7543	3.4359
		2	11.2320	6.5230	0.9000	10.0373	2.1517	10.4683	0.9000
	High	1	3.0642	5.0619	1.7200	19.2331	2.6034	3.9036	1.7200
		2	1.6268	1.8247	0.2762	15.5020	1.6993	1.9098	0.2762

5.2.2 Motion Consistency Analysis

Besides tracking accuracy, motion consistency is also very important for painting applications, particularly regarding the constant flow rate of the painting gun. To assess the motion consistency, two criteria are used: position fluctuation perpendicular to the painting surface and speed fluctuation. Figures 13 and 14 show the position and speed deviation of the painting robot and the detailed metrics are given in Tables 6 and 7.

Fig. 13. Position deviation.

Table 6

Errors in position perpendicular to the painting surface. (Unit: $\times 10^{-5}$ m)

Trajectory	Speed	Control Parameter Set	Average error	Maximum error	Standard deviation
1	Low	1	2.8464	14.5315	2.8436
		2	1.2516	6.7795	1.2442
	High	1	2.8012	12.5132	2.7974
		2	1.3301	3.6955	1.3008
2	Low	1	1.7093	13.976	1.7094
		2	0.9515	7.7253	0.9515
	High	1	1.0784	8.0714	1.0781
		2	0.6337	3.0772	0.633
1'	Low	1	2.8600	10.9134	2.8449
		2	1.3150	4.0669	1.2779
	High	1	1.8797	5.1090	1.5559
		2	1.1949	3.1998	0.8975
2'	Low	1	1.2485	7.1535	1.2470
		2	0.8004	3.0762	0.8004
	High	1	0.6792	2.6931	0.6494
		2	0.4364	1.3959	0.4205

Fig. 14. Speed deviation.

Table 7

Errors in end speed. (Unit: $\times 10^{-4}$ m/s)

Trajectory	Speed	Control Parameter Set	Average error	Maximum error	Standard deviation
1	Low	1	6.3346	21.9035	3.1963
		2	5.5227	21.4963	2.8554
	High	1	8.7490	28.9781	4.6853
		2	6.1723	22.2872	3.3379
2	Low	1	4.2816	24.7895	2.6667
		2	3.9751	16.7879	2.4805
	High	1	7.5460	37.2427	5.1441
		2	5.6563	25.0097	3.8472
1'	Low	1	5.9969	19.8885	2.7560
		2	4.9205	21.4963	2.3833
	High	1	5.3420	12.9025	2.1704
		2	4.2797	12.8579	1.9514
2'	Low	1	2.5428	14.3894	1.2725
		2	2.3309	16.7879	1.1975
	High	1	4.0653	18.2943	2.8566
		2	3.5611	17.9361	2.5232

The most crucial considerations are the standard deviations of position and speed errors during the painting session, which decrease by approximately 55.1% and 13.5% under low speed and 42.3% and 10.1% under high speed for Trajectory 1, respectively. For Trajectory 2, these deviations decrease by about 35.8%, 5.9%, 35.3% and 11.7%, respectively. Moreover, the average error also witnesses a substantial decrease. Therefore, through experiments for different trajectories under different operating speeds, the proposed strategy proves highly effective in designing control parameters for robots with parallelogram linkages.

6 Conclusions

This paper investigates the dynamic characteristics and control parameter design method of a painting robot with parallelogram linkages. The dynamics of the robot's parallel part have three key characteristics. 1) The inertia force is independent of the serial part, with its diagonal terms being constant and dominant in their corresponding rows. 2) The gravitational force exhibits independence among joints, and can be linearly approximated. 3) There lacks a coupling term in the centrifugal and Coriolis force, which is also negligible. Based on the time-invariant and decoupling dynamics, a novel theory-experiment mixed two-step approach to design control parameters is proposed. Experiments where the robot follows trajectories for painting an airplane wing demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed method, which showcase significant reductions in tracking error and improvement in motion consistency compared with the traditional control parameter design method. In further study, we will explore the impact of parallelogram linkages on the serial part and try to mitigate the coupling effects between them by optimizing our design and control strategy.

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